

**DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING OF SECONDARY SCHOOL
PUPILS ON A BASE OF ENGLISH PROVERBS AND SAYING**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10008110>

ANNOTATION: The article describes the technology development of critical thinking which is interrelated on a base of English proverbs and sayings. The article shows the use of a number of interactive methods.

KEYWORDS: Thinking, intelligence, critical thinking, technologies of training in thinking, mind mapping, Venn diagram, fishbone

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common genres of oral folk art in any country are proverbs and sayings, the time of occurrence of which is not known, but the fact that this is the most fertile material for learning a foreign language remains indisputable. Early sources describe the use of proverbs in England as one of the effective tools in teaching Latin. In proverbs and sayings a large part of human experience is formed. Owing to its generalized nature, proverbs and sayings can be used at all levels of foreign language teaching in teaching the art of allegory, the ability to illustrate one's thought and summarize it in a short form. The use of proverbs and sayings in a foreign language lesson will certainly contribute to a better mastery of this subject, expanding knowledge of the language, vocabulary and the developing of critical thinking of the learners. The purpose of this work is to analyze and summarize the experience of working with proverbs and sayings in English lessons and its efficiency in elaboration of critical thinking. [1.199]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Below we look at a number of techniques that develop critical thinking through proverbs and sayings.

Writing an opinion-essay

One of the methods for developing students' critical thinking is writing an essay. Essay writing helps students develop the ability to analyze information; the ability to summarize information and combine judgments of evidence to form one's own opinion, as well as the ability to present one's point of view in a reasonable, organized and persuasive manner.

An essay is a written form that reflects the impressions, thoughts and experiences of the student on a particular topic. Depending on the purpose of

writing, the content is also selected by the author. The topic of the essay is selected from the proposed proverbs / sayings in English that are directly related to the topic. Almost all sayings and proverbs in the English language in one way or another serve as proven advice on how to live, eat, work and rest in order to keep your body in good shape.

Mind mapping. Mind mapping was developed as an effective method for generating ideas by association. In order to create a mind map, you usually start in the middle of the page with the central theme/main idea and from that point you work outward in all directions to create a growing diagram composed of keywords, phrases, concepts, facts and figures. It can be used for assignments and essay writing especially in the initial stages, where it is an ideal strategy to use for your 'thinking'. Mind mapping can be used for generating, visualising, organising, note-taking, problem-solving, decision-making, revising and clarifying your university topic, so that you can get started with assessment tasks. Essentially, a mind map is used to 'brainstorm' a topic and is a great strategy for students.

A cause and effect diagram, often called a **"fishbone"** diagram, can help in brainstorming to identify possible causes of a problem and in sorting ideas into useful categories. A fishbone diagram is a visual way to look at cause and effect. It is a more structured approach than some other tools available for brainstorming causes of a problem (e.g., the Five Whys tool). The problem or effect is displayed at the head or mouth of the fish. Possible contributing causes are listed on the smaller "bones" under various cause categories.

Pic 1. Structure of Mind mapping

A **Venn diagram** is an illustration that uses circles to show the relationships among things or finite groups of things. Circles that overlap have a commonality while circles that do not overlap do not share those traits. [2.256]

Venn diagrams help to visually represent the similarities and differences between two concepts. They have long been recognized for their usefulness as educational tools. Since the mid-20th century, Venn diagrams have been used as part of the introductory logic curriculum and in elementary-level educational plans around the world.

CONCLUSION

The result is an unusual level of confidence in your results, and empowered decision-making along with it. In addition, it is a very effective recourse for involving children in critical thinking in which you need to take the job as a team, creating, for example, the script actions and deeds. One of the most important aspects is the ability to think critical.

References:

1. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2020). Technologies of developing the ecological culture of students in the process of learning a foreign languages in higher educational institutions. *Solid State Technology*, 63(1s), 1816-1825.
2. Kuzibaevna, O. G. (2021). Analysis of Effective Ways to Develop Students' Environmental Culture in Foreign Language Teaching. *Central asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(12), 37-43.
3. Обидова, Г. (2021). Развитие экологической культуры в образовательных моделях развитых стран мира. *Общество и инновации*, 2(10/S), 251-256.
4. Tadjibaeva, A., & Tashlanova, N. (2020). The collaborative approach in content and language learning. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (6 (60)), 31-34.
5. Mamatovich, Z. R., & Ergashevna, T. A. (2019). Blended learning in higher education using LMS Moodle. *Образовательный процесс*, (5 (16)), 5-9.
6. Ergashevna, T. A. (2020). Specific features of the language in the development of culture. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (3 (148)), 82-84.
7. Mukhammad, K. K., & ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022, December). THE ESSENCE OF NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES* (Vol. 1, No. 19, pp. 91-93).
8. ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3 (10), 126-128.

9. Sarvinoz, T., & Shodiya, I. (2022). TILSHUNOSLIKDA KOGNITIV LINGVISTIKA SHAKLLANISH TARIXIGA DOIR. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(13), 51-54.
10. Ibragimjonovna, A. M. (2023). The Issues Related to Studying of Language and thought in Cognitive Linguistics. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 31, 271-273.
11. Toshpulatova, M., & Ilhomjonova, R. (2023). TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY. *Engineering problems and innovations*.
12. Toshpulatova, M. I. (2022). The main features in teaching English for specific purposes. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(5), 207-214.
13. Ikromovna, T. M. (2022). USE OF FOLKTALES IN ENGLISH LESSONS. *POLISH SCIENCE JOURNAL*, 88.
14. Parpiyeva, M., & Jurayeva, M. (2023). Problems of linguoculturological and neurolinguistic study of phonetic means. *American Journal Of Philological Sciences*, 3(02), 49-59.
15. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & SultanovnaUsmanova, S. (2023). Neyrolingvistika sohasini organish tendensiyalari. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 2(1), 53-59.
16. Abdug'ofur qizi Jurayeva, M., & Alisher o'g'li, M. M. (2023). Morphology and syntax and crosslinguistic findings in neurolinguistics. *Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, 18(8), 156-159.
17. Dilshoda, R. (2022). THE STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 20(2), 36-40.
18. Raximjonova, D. (2022). INGLIZ VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA KOMPOZITSIYA USULIDA SO 'Z YASALISHI HODISASINING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(4), 710-713.
19. Raximjonova, D. (2023). STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF COMPUTER SOFTWARE TERMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS. *Farg 'ona davlat universiteti ilmiy jurnali*, (1), 448-452.
20. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). The Cognitive Aspect of the Purpose of Teaching Foreign Languages. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 16, 88-94.
21. Djuraevna, T. N. (2023). Language Education as A System: Structure, Functions and Main Components. *Periodica Journal of Modern Philosophy, Social Sciences and Humanities*, 14, 141-146.
22. Djurayevna, T. N. (2022). Semantic and structural features of the vocabulary of color designation in english, uzbek and russian languages. *Global Book Publishing Services*, 01-123.

23. Juraeva, Z. Q. (2017). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE. Форум молодых ученых, (5 (9)), 5-9.